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Effect of Instructional Materials on Academic Achievement in Mensuration among Senior Secondary Students in Dutsin-Ma Education Zone, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of instructional materials on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in mensuration within the Dutsin-Ma Education Zone, Katsina State. A total of 210 out of 4,129 public senior secondary two (SS II) Mathematics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Dutsin-Ma Education Zone, Katsina State were randomly selected. A specially constructed and validated test, "Students' Mensuration Achievement Test (SMAT)," with reliability coefficient of 0.83 was used to collect data. Data collected was analyzed through descriptive statistics for research questions and t-test to test hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Results indicated that students taught with instructional materials performed significantly better than those without, with no notable gender difference in achievement. Recommendations include supplying instructional materials to enhance mathematics teaching in Katsina State.

Keywords: *Instructional materials, Achievement, Gender, Mathematics, Mensuration.*

Introduction

Mathematics is essential in a child's education as it applies to many everyday activities. It serves as a foundation for scientific discoveries and inventions (Salman, 2005). A strong grasp of mathematics is necessary since scientific findings are often expressed mathematically (Onyido, 2002). Without basic mathematical skills, a society risks falling behind in global scientific advancements. Therefore, mathematics is mandatory in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria, and a credit pass is typically required for admission to most tertiary institutions.

Secondary school mathematics includes algebra, mensuration, statistics, number and numeration, geometry, and trigonometry. Mensuration involves measuring and calculating the lengths, areas, and volumes of geometric shapes using known dimensions and formulas. According to Weatheril (2004), it

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is key in problem-solving, while Adolphus (2011) notes that topics like plane and solid shapes are often difficult, leading to poor student performance. Research shows that many students approach mensuration questions haphazardly or avoid them, especially in essay-type tests (WAEC, 2007).

The teaching and learning of mathematics face numerous challenges, resulting in poor student achievement. Researchers and educators have identified inadequate instructional materials and facilities as key issues impacting performance (Akolo, 2010; Anyichie & Onyedike, 2012; Onwuka & Moseri, 2011). The goals of mathematics education remain unmet due to ineffective teaching methods and insufficient materials to engage students. Incorporating various instructional materials, such as concrete objects and teaching aids, is essential for meaningful learning. This study aims to investigate the effect of these materials on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in mensuration.

Instructional materials are essential tools that enhance teaching and make learning more accessible. According to Olayinka (2016), they improve teachers' effectiveness and boost student performance. Fadeiye (2005) defines them as visual and audio-visual aids, as well as tangible and intangible items that elevate teaching quality. Isola (2010) describes them as objects that help present lessons logically and sequentially, making learning more engaging and encouraging active participation. Additionally, these materials facilitate skill acquisition while promoting self-confidence among learners. Obanya (2004) noted that studies in Nigeria showed poor results in senior school certificate examinations, with only about 10% of candidates "meaningfully passing." Abdu-Raheem (2011) identified inadequate instructional materials as a key factor behind the school system's ineffectiveness and poor student performance. Ahmed (2003) added that many Nigerian secondary schools lack conducive learning environments and essential resources. Eniayewu (2005) emphasized that instructional materials are vital for effective teaching, helping students acquire knowledge and uphold academic standards.

Despite the significance of instructional materials in facilitating practical learning and knowledge acquisition, they are often not readily available in Nigerian secondary schools, which contributes to low achievement levels among students in government examinations (Abdu-Raheem, 2014). As a solution, he encouraged teachers to improvise teaching aids, as these can significantly enhance student participation during lessons and foster inquiry, problem-solving, discussions, and clarifications among students and teachers.

Achievement is a critical measurement variable in this context. It refers to the completion of goals that individuals set for themselves (Manion, 2014). According to Dogo et al. (2017), achievement is defined as the ability to successfully perform a given task using appropriate knowledge, effort, and skills. Therefore, when students earn credit passes in mathematics at the West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (WASSCE), they are achieving a key learning goal.

Achievement varies across genders, and research on gender issues in academic achievement shows mixed results. While some studies indicate that male students perform better than their female counterparts, others suggest the opposite. Additionally, some research has found no significant difference in the mathematical achievement of male and female students. For instance, Ogunkunle (2007) and Usman and Musa (2015) found a significant difference in mean achievement scores

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favoring male students. Conversely, Ozomadu (2006), Galadima and Okogbenin (2012), and Attah and Guwam (2015) reported that gender does not significantly affect students' achievement in mathematics. Meanwhile, Akande (2017) noted a significant difference favoring female students in mathematics achievement. These conflicting results highlight the need for further investigation. Consequently, this study aims to explore gender differences in mensuration achievement when students are taught using instructional materials.

Statement of the Research Problem

Mathematics is a challenging subject for many secondary school students, leading to high failure rates in examinations (Akhter & Akhter, 2018; Ehiwario, et al., 2020). This issue has raised concerns among educators and researchers, as studies indicate that ineffective teaching methods and insufficient instructional materials contribute to poor performance. Despite previous research on improving mathematics achievement through these materials, the issue remains unresolved, especially in the Dutsin-Ma Education Zone. This study thus, aims to investigate the effect of instructional materials on the academic achievement of senior secondary students in mensuration in this region.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of instructional materials on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in mensuration. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of instructional materials on the achievement of senior secondary school students in mensuration;
2. Find the effect of instructional materials on the achievement of male and female senior secondary school students in mensuration;

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mensuration using instructional materials and those taught without instructional materials?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mensuration using instructional materials?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at $\rho \leq 0.05$ level of significance;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mensuration using instructional materials and those taught without instructional materials.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mensuration using instructional materials.

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Methodology

Research Design: The study used a non-randomized, quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test involving an experimental group and a control group. Intact classes were assigned to each group, consisting of both male and female students. A pretest was conducted to ensure the groups were equivalent. The experimental group learned mensuration using instructional materials, while the control group received the same instruction without materials for 6 weeks. A post-test was given to both groups to evaluate the impact of instructional materials on students' academic achievement in mensuration.

Population and Sample: The study targeted SS II students from all public senior secondary schools in the Dutsin-Ma education zone, Katsina State, totaling 4,129 students (2,479 males and 1,650 females) across 17 schools (Source: Zonal Education Quality Assurance Dutsin-Ma, 2024). SS II students were chosen for their stability at the senior secondary level. A simple random sampling technique was used to select four co-educational schools from the 17. After administering a pretest, two schools with similar performance were selected, resulting in a sample of 210 students: 106 students (68 males, 38 females) in the experimental group and 104 students (75 males, 29 females) in the control group.

Instrumentation: The data collection instrument was the "Students' Mensuration Achievement Test (SMAT)," which consisted of two sections. Section A collected personal information, including school name, class, serial number, and gender. Section B featured 40 multiple-choice questions on mensuration concepts, scored with one point for each correct answer, totaling a maximum of 40 marks. The SMAT was administered as both a pre-test and a post-test, each lasting one hour, to assess students' academic achievement before and after the treatment. Completed tests were collected on the same day.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument: The instrument, SMAT was face and content validated by three mathematics education experts and pilot-tested on a separate group of similar students. The test-retest method established reliability, with a Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.83, deemed adequate.

Data Collection and Analysis: The researchers, assisted by research assistants in each of the secondary schools, administered SMAT after treatment. The scores were statistically analyzed to address research questions and test null hypotheses. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while a t-test at a 0.05 significance level, performed using SPSS, was used to test the null hypotheses.

Presentation of Results:

Research question 1: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mensuration using instructional materials and those taught without instructional materials?

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Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Pre-test and Post-test Achievement Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

S/N	Group	Pre-Test					Post-Test				
		N	\bar{X}	SD	SE	MD	\bar{X}	SD	SE	MD	
1.	Experimental	106	17.58	3.55	0.34	-0.31	28.08	3.68	0.36	5.72	
2.	Control	104	17.89	2.41	0.24		22.36	2.95	0.29		

NOTE: N = Sample Size, Mean, SD = Std. Deviation, SE = Std. Error, MD = Mean difference

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 1 shows the pre-treatment mean achievement scores for the experimental group (17.58, SD = 3.55) and the control group (17.89, SD = 2.41), with a mean difference of 0.31, indicating similar abilities. In the post-test, the experimental group scored 28.08 (SD = 3.68), while the control group scored 22.36 (SD = 2.95), resulting in a mean difference of 5.72. Both groups improved from pre-test to post-test, but the experimental group's score was significantly higher. Further inferential statistics will determine if this difference is statistically significant.

Research question 2: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mensuration using instructional materials?

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of Post-test Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

S/N	Group	N	Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Mean Difference
1.	Male	68	28.31	3.46	0.42	0.65
2.	Female	38	27.66	4.08	0.66	

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 2 showed that male students in the experimental group had a mean achievement score of 28.31 (SD = 3.46), while female students scored a mean of 27.66 (SD = 4.08), resulting in a mean difference of 0.65, indicating slightly higher performance by males. Inferential statistical analysis is needed to determine if this difference is significant.

Research Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mensuration using instructional materials and those taught without instructional materials.

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Table 3: Post-test t-test Analysis of Achievement Scores of Students Taught Mensuration in the Experimental and Control Groups.

S/N	Group	N	X	SD	df	t.cal	t.crit	ρ-value	Decision
1.	Experimental	106	28.08	3.68	208	12.41	1.97	0.001*	S
2.	Control	104	22.36	2.95					

*Significant

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 3 showed a significant difference in academic achievement of experimental and control groups at the 0.05 significance level ($df = 208$), with a p -value of 0.001 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating that students taught mensuration with instructional materials (mean = 28.08) performed better than those taught without them (mean = 22.36). Consequently, the hypothesis stating no significant difference in mean achievement scores was rejected. This suggests that using instructional materials in teaching mensuration is more effective in enhancing students' academic achievement.

Research Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mensuration using instructional materials.

Table 4: Post-test t-test Analysis of Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group.

S/N	Group	N	X	SD	df	t.cal	t.crit	ρ-value	Decision
1.	Male	68	28.31	3.46	104	0.87	1.98	0.39	NS
2.	Female	38	27.66	4.08					

Not Significant at $p > 0.05$ level

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 4 showed that $t_{cal} = 0.87 < t_{crit} = 1.98$ at 0.05 significance level with degree of freedom (df) = 104. Alternatively, the p -value of 0.39 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 which is an indication that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught mensuration using instructional materials. The mean score of 28.31 of the male students is not statistically different from the mean score of 27.66 of the female students. Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected. In essence, the male and female students performed equally well when taught mensuration using instructional materials.

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Summary of Major Findings

The major findings of the study are presented as follows:

1. There was a significant difference between the post-test mean achievement of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group.
2. There was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental group. The results showed that instructional materials can improve the academic achievement of male and female students equally.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the effect of instructional materials on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in mensuration within the Dutsin-ma education zone, Katsina state. An experimental group was taught using these materials, while a control group received the same instruction without them. Both groups were pre-tested and post-tested to assess their academic performance. The results indicated that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group, demonstrating that instructional materials positively enhance academic achievement in mensuration. This supports previous research by Enohuan (2015), Olayinka (2016), and Adebule and Ayoola (2016), which also found that students taught with instructional materials do better. Ehiosu (2008) identified several essential roles of instructional materials, including stimulating student interest and providing meaningful information.

The second hypothesis explored gender differences in academic achievement with the use of instructional materials. Post-test results showed no significant difference in performance between male and female students, suggesting that both genders benefited equally from the materials. This finding contradicts earlier studies asserting gender disparities in mathematics achievement (Ogunkunle, 2007; Usman & Musa, 2015) who reported that male students excelled in mathematics than female students, and (Akande, 2017; Muhammad & Maitama, 2018) who noted superior performance by female students; but aligns with other research by Ozomadu (2006), Isaya and Thankgah (2007), Afolabi and Adeleke (2010), Oladejo et al. (2011), Galadima and Okogbenin (2012), Muodumogu and Yisa (2013), Attah and Guwam (2015), and Ayoola (2015), indicating no significant differences. Overall, the study concludes that instructional materials offer equitable learning opportunities for all students.

Conclusion

This study shows that students taught with instructional materials achieve higher scores than those without. Additionally, there is no significant difference in achievement between male and female students using these materials. Thus, incorporating instructional materials in teaching mensuration positively affects students' academic success in the Dutsin-Ma Education Zone of Katsina State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings emanating from this study, the following recommendations are suggested: -

1. The Katsina State Government, through the Ministry of Education, should provide instructional materials to senior secondary schools to facilitate effective teaching and learning of Mathematics concepts in Katsina State.

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2. Other stakeholders, such as the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA), should also contribute by providing teaching materials to schools.
3. Teachers should receive comprehensive training on how to use instructional materials through regular workshops and seminars.
4. The Katsina State Government, via the Ministry of Education, should ensure regular supervision to promote the effective use of instructional materials and resources in the teaching of Mathematics in schools.

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